

STRUCTURAL AND SEMANTIC CLASSIFICATION OF “HEAD / BAS” SOMATIC IDIOMS IN ENGLISH AND KARAKALPAK

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Abstract. *Somatic idioms constitute an essential part of the phraseological system of any language, reflecting both universal cognitive mechanisms and culture-specific conceptualizations. Among somatic components, the lexeme head in English and bas in Karakalpak occupies a central position, as it is closely associated with such abstract notions as intellect, leadership, control, and emotional states. This paper aims to provide a structural and semantic classification of somatic idioms in English and Karakalpak that contain the components head and bas. The research employs descriptive, comparative, and semantic methods of analysis. The findings demonstrate that while the structural models and semantic fields of the analyzed idioms show certain similarities, they also reveal significant differences обусловленные linguistic typology and national-cultural background. The study contributes to the field of comparative phraseology and may be applied in translation studies and foreign language teaching.*

Keywords: *somatic idioms, phraseology, head, bas, structural classification, semantic classification, comparative linguistics*

Phraseological units are considered essential tools for verbalizing human experience and worldview in contemporary linguistics. Among them, somatic idioms hold a special place, as they involve names of body parts and are inherently anthropocentric. Somatic idioms not only allow researchers to identify universal cognitive patterns but also reveal culture-specific features embedded in a language [Baker, 2011, p. 67].

The lexemes *head* in English and *bas* in Karakalpak are among the most productive somatic elements in idiomatic constructions. Traditionally associated with intellect, reasoning, leadership, and control, these elements are actively involved in idioms expressing both rational and emotional aspects. Although interest in somatic phraseology is growing, comparative structural and semantic studies of English and Karakalpak idioms containing these elements remain limited, which highlights the relevance of the present research.

This study aims to classify somatic idioms containing *head* and *bas* at both structural and semantic levels and to identify similarities and differences between these elements in English and Karakalpak. The findings provide a foundation for further research in comparative phraseology, translation studies, and language teaching.

Somatic idioms are defined as fixed phraseological structures that include names of human body parts and serve as figurative expressions of human experience [Cruse, 2000, p. 118]. Somatic elements play a significant role in shaping idiomatic meaning, as the human body is one of the primary sources of conceptualization. Features of phraseological units with somatic components include semantic integrity, metaphorical motivation, and cultural markedness. These idioms are

widely used in both speech and writing and function as stylistic, expressive, and communicative tools.

Linguists classify idioms according to structural, semantic, and functional approaches. The structural approach examines the grammatical composition of idioms, including verbal, nominal, adjectival, and compound constructions. The semantic approach analyzes the underlying meanings conveyed by idioms and categorizes them according to themes such as cognition, emotion, leadership, and self-regulation. Functional approaches view idioms as instruments of pragmatic and discourse strategies, including humor, persuasion, and rhetorical emphasis.

Thus, the subordinative connection of components within many phraseological and idiomatic units has been established. Over time, each element became fixed in the language and subsequently transformed into a metaphorically stable phrase. Such phrases convey subtle meanings and emotions, but they must be used with caution, as they can sometimes be perceived as offensive or indecent and carry a negative connotation [S. Arzımbetova, 2024, p 56].

Comparative phraseology emphasizes the importance of cross-linguistic analysis in identifying universal patterns as well as language-specific peculiarities. English idioms often rely on abstract metaphors and figurative expressions, whereas Karakalpak idioms frequently utilize agglutinative morphology and agglutinative references. Understanding these differences is essential for effective translation, language teaching, and intercultural communication [Temirova, 2015, p. 47].

The structural analysis of English and Karakalpak idioms containing the lexemes *head* and *bas* can be categorized as follows:

1. **Verbal Idioms:** These idioms are composed of a verb and a somatic noun, typically describing actions related to emotional or mental states. Examples include the English *to lose one's head* (to panic or act irrationally), *keep one's head* and the Karakalpak *bası qaq jarlıw*, (lose one's temper), *bas tartıw* (pass the buck). Most verbal idioms are context-dependent and convey dynamic behaviors.
2. **Nominal Idioms:** In these idioms, the somatic noun serves as the head of a nominal phrase, reflecting character traits or social roles. Examples are English *big-headed*, *head of the department* and Karakalpak “*jurt basi*”, “*jil basi*”. Nominal idioms often rely on metaphorical extensions of body parts to express abstract qualities.
3. **Adjectival and Predicative Idioms:** These constructions combine adjectives or participles with a somatic noun, typically expressing emotional characteristics or temperament. Examples include English *hot-headed* and Karakalpak *qızğan bas* (quick-tempered), *qara basi* (alone). Such constructions illustrate how languages encode affective states through body-part metaphors.
4. **Compound / Multi-word Idioms:** These idioms incorporate the somatic noun within a broader metaphorical structure. For instance, English *keep a head* (to remain calm), *keep a cool head* and Karakalpak *basın tik tutıw*, *bas awırtıw* represent behavioral control and social guidance. Compound idioms highlight the extension of body-part metaphors into complex semantic structures.

Semantic analysis examines the meanings of idioms containing the lexemes *head* and *bas*. The key semantic fields include:

1. **Intellect / Cognitive Activity:** Idioms referring to thinking, problem-solving, or mental effort. Examples include English *to use one's head* (think carefully) and Karakalpak *basın qıynap oylaw* (think hard). These idioms emphasize rationality and decision-making.

2. **Leadership / Authority:** Idioms expressing social control, responsibility, or authority. Examples are English *head of the department* and Karakalpak *úy bası* (head of household). These reflect culturally entrenched concepts of power and position.
3. **Emotion / Temper:** Idioms conveying feelings or emotional states. English *hot-headed* (*quick-tempered, easily angered*), *lose one's head* (*panic, lose control of oneself emotionally*), *level-headed* (*calm, not easily upset*) and Karakalpak *bas qızgán* denote quick-tempered or emotionally volatile behavior. Such idioms demonstrate the close link between physical metaphors and emotional concepts.
4. **Control / Self-Regulation:** Idioms related to composure, calmness, or self-control. Examples include English *keep a cool head*, *keep a level head*, *keep one's head* and Karakalpak *basın tik tutıw*. These idioms often provide social guidance, personal advice, or moral instruction.

Comparative analysis highlights both universal patterns and language-specific features in somatic idioms. Across cultures, humans commonly conceptualize the head as the center of thought, leadership, and emotion, which explains similarities in semantic categories between English and Karakalpak idioms. Structurally, verbal and nominal constructions dominate, and both languages use metaphorical extensions of body parts [Saeed, 2016, p. 319].

Typological and cultural differences create divergences. English idioms frequently employ prepositional phrases, phrasal verbs, and abstract constructions, whereas Karakalpak idioms often use agglutinative morphology, possessive suffixes, and culturally grounded elements. For instance, English *to use one's head* carries a neutral connotation of cognitive strategy, while Karakalpak *bas almaw* (*tinbay islew*), *jumısqa bası menen kirip ketiw* additionally implies diligence, persistence, or effort towards achieving a goal.

Pragmatic and discourse differences are also evident. English idioms commonly appear in colloquial speech, literature, and media, while Karakalpak idioms are often found in proverbs, folk speech, and community advice.

The somatic elements *head* in English and *bas* in Karakalpak serve as central components in idioms relating to intellect, emotion, leadership, and control. Both common patterns and language-specific features emerge in structural and semantic classifications. This study contributes to comparative phraseology and provides practical insights for translation, foreign language teaching, and cross-cultural communication. Further research could explore additional somatic elements and examine how they interact with cultural metaphors to enhance understanding of human thought and expression.

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